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Мирзо Улугбека.***Email:**azamatkhidirnazarov1985@gmail.com**©2023. Khidirnazarov
Azamat Mamarajabovich.****O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA TARKIBIY
O'ZGARISHLARNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR
YO'NALISHLARI (sanoat misolida)****PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF
STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN THE ECONOMY OF
UZBEKISTAN (for the example of the industry)****ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ
СТРУКТУРНЫХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ В ЭКОНОМИКЕ
УЗБЕКИСТАНА (на примере промышленности)****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada iqtisodiyotda tarkibiy o'zgarishlarni amalga oshirish istiqbollari va imkoniyatlari sanoat misolida tahliliy tavsiflangan. Unda sanoatlashgan jamiyat va to'rtinchi sanoat inqilobi ta'kidlangan. Sohadagi tarkibiy o'zgarishlar bugungi kunda iqtisodiyotning jadal rivojlanishiga sabab bo'lganligi ta'kidlandi.

ANNOTATION

In this article, the prospects and possibilities of implementing structural changes in the economy were analytically described on the example of industry. It emphasized the industrialized society and the fourth industrial revolution. It was argued that the structural changes in the industry are the reason for the rapid development of the economy today.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье были аналитически описаны перспективы и возможности осуществления структурных изменений в экономике на примере промышленности. В ней особое внимание уделялось индустриализированному обществу и четвертой промышленной революции. Утверждалось, что структурные изменения в промышленности являются причиной быстрого развития экономики сегодня.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

qishloq xo'jaligi, sanoat, ishlab chiqarish, sanoat tarmoqlari, tarkibiy o'zgarishlar, sanoatlashgan jamiyat, to'rtinchi sanoat inqilobi

KEYWORDS

agriculture, industry, production, industrial sectors, structural changes, industrialized society, fourth industrial revolution

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

сельское хозяйство, промышленность, производство, промышленные секторы, структурные изменения, промышленно развитое общество, четвертая промышленная революция

INTRODUCTION

Industry 4.0 is a leading industry that affects production in society and the level of development in the economy. The industry for itself and for other sectors of the national economy is engaged in the production of equipment and products, as well as raw materials, fuel extraction, energy production, wood preparation, processing and processing of products (factories, factories, power plants, mines, mines, etc.) complex. Industry forms the basis of expanded reproduction and provides industrial growth.

According to some scientists, the main criterion for the formation of an industrialized society in a country is that no more than 50% of the working-age population should be in agriculture. This criterion allows to identify industrialized countries.

Industry refers to a complex of enterprises that produce raw materials, materials, fuel, energy and other products or provide services to the population.

MAIN PART

The emergence of industry as an independent branch of social production is connected with the separation of handicrafts from agriculture - the second largest division of labor. Capitalist industry appeared in the Western European countries in the 14th and 15th centuries and passed through the stages of simple capitalist cooperation, manufacture and large-scale machine industry - factory. At the end of the 18th and the beginning of the 19th century, the transition from the manufacture to the machine industry was an industrial revolution, first in England, and later in other European countries. took a nap. In Russia and some other countries, the industry developed in the form of manufacture from the beginning of the 18th century, and the machine industry developed from the second half of the 19th century.

The roots of industrial development on the territory of Uzbekistan are the crafts with a long history. In cities like Samarkand, Bukhara, Urganch, Tashkent, Ko'kan, Margilon, Namangan, Andijan, small and large crafts developed. In the emergence of a new era of industry in Uzbekistan, Russian

industrialists and Russian capital entered, and primary processing industries (cotton ginning, wine, vodka, canning, cotton oil factories) appeared, and the industry in Uzbekistan developed in connection with the Russian industry and economy.

According to the classification adopted in the 80s of the 20th century, the Industry is divided into 18 major branches: electrical energy; fuel industry; ferrous metallurgy; non-ferrous metallurgy; chemical and petrochemical industry; engineering and metalworking; wood processing and pulp and paper industry; building materials industry; construction and detailing industry; glass and porcelain industry; light industry; food industry; microbiology industry; flour and feed industry; medical industry; printing industry. These industries, in turn, are grouped into processing industries and collecting industries.

The aero-space industry is also developed in developed space countries.

Over the next 100 years, the industries of Uzbekistan included electric power, gas, oil, coal, ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy, agricultural machinery (tractors, cotton picking machines), automobile engineering, cable, electronics, cotton ginning machinery, irrigation and construction machinery, chemistry, cement, building materials, medicine, oil, textile, tailoring, food and other industries were formed.

Industrialized society is a society formed in the process and as a result of industrialization, development of machine production, improvement of labor organization, application of achievements of scientific and technical development. It is characterized by mass production, labor mechanization and automation, the development of the goods and services market, the humanization of economic relations, the increasing role of management, and the formation of civil society.

Fundamental industrial reforms were carried out in the economy of Uzbekistan, industrial enterprises in many sectors were taken out of state control and privatized, and transformed into state-joint-stock, corporate,

collective, private and other forms of organizational and legal ownership. Structural restructuring was carried out in industrial sectors, which play an important role in the republic's economy, and many small and medium-sized enterprises were established. In cooperation with foreign capital, joint ventures were established in many industries.

Industrialized society is an industry-based society with flexible dynamic structures, which is characterized by: division of labor and growth of its productivity, high level of competition, rapid development of entrepreneurial resources and human capital, development of civil society. society and management systems at all levels, extensive development of information and communication

technologies (ICT), a high level of urbanization and an increase in the quality of life.

Industrialized society stems from the Industrial Revolution. There is a redistribution of labor force: employment in agriculture will decrease from 70-80% to 10-15%, as a result of which the share of employment in industry, trade and other non-agricultural employment sectors will increase. It leads to an increase in the share of the urban population (80-85%).

What are the opportunities for Uzbekistan during the fourth industrial revolution?

Today, opinions are being put forward that the fourth industrial revolution is about to begin. So, what will the next revolution be characterized by?

Photo: https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/To%CA%BBritinchi_sanoat_inqilobi

The concept of the industrial revolution, at the initial stage, meant the process of replacing manual labor in production by machines, and it began with changes in the textile industry in Great Britain in the 18th century.

Due to the need to meet the high demand for gas, the first industrial revolution, which began with the discovery of the loom and the steam

power to move it, ended with the introduction of machine production in factories.

Since this period, mankind has implemented the second and third industrial revolutions, which are the basis of scientific and technical development. Each era had its own characteristics, positive and negative consequences that affected the fate of nations and states.

The countries that started on the path of "Rapid Development" on time achieved high development indicators, but some countries lagged behind.

When did the fourth industrial revolution appear?

Revolutionary changes were manifested, first of all, in the field of technology. The increasing penetration of nanotechnology, artificial intelligence, social networks, and green energy sources into production, services, and everyday life has begun to renew the way of life of a person.

Global demand for artificial intelligence technologies by companies has grown by 72 percent, and they have been introduced in the largest volumes in such areas as information technology, marketing, finance and accounting.

Secondly, as a result of changes in the current world order, international relations and trade moved from the Atlantic Ocean to the Pacific Ocean. Beijing's role in economic and political decisions has increased significantly. This was influenced by the change in the nature of technological discoveries in China.

Until the first decade of the 21st century, Chinese companies, which mainly copied technologies from Western countries, have now developed their research capabilities. Huawei Corporation, a small sample, holds more than 33 percent of the 5G Internet market, or more than a third, and is leading the way in innovation.

Thirdly generation, a layer of "Zoomers" (enlarged, fast) has grown, which is fundamentally different from "Millennials" (ordinary, middle level) in the psychology and behavior of generations. The main limiting factor of the new generation is that the Internet has entered their lifestyle.

For those born after 1996-1997, they imagine the world before the Internet differently. By the time of the fourth industrial revolution, these young people are entering the labor market.

Generally speaking, the industrial revolution directly or indirectly affects not only the economy, but also human behavior and international political processes.

Opportunities of Uzbekistan in the new period

In Uzbekistan, the share of young people dominates the demographic distribution of the population and is expected to grow in the future.

One of the factors that shaped the fourth industrial revolution is the age group known as "Zoomers", they can play the main role in bringing innovation to the economy.

First of all, this generation is distinguished from older people by its interest in technology and techniques and the ability to easily deal with inventions.

Secondly, they are active consumers of innovation that they can produce. In such a situation, the state has only the task of properly

directing the education system and fairly defining and regulating the economic rules between the newly stratified groups that become producers and consumers.

As another enabling factor, we can cite the fact that the Fourth Industrial Revolution is taking place together with changes in the world order. China is emerging as a center of technological and technical processes that determine artificial intelligence, green energy, nanotechnology and similar changes.

If we consider China's geopolitical location opportunities and innovative achievements, the possibility of receiving technological advances from Uzbekistan's close neighbor will increase. According to analysts, the "Spillover effect" in the economy can help to advance the development of the regions close to it by 0.7%.

Coordination of legal processes related to licenses, patents, customs policy and industrial zones appears as a task before the state.

CONCLUSION

The final and most important factor of the fourth industrial revolution is the stage of invention, development and effective use of new types of technology that we mentioned at the beginning. For example, today, the aerospace industry is rapidly developing and becoming one of the most important sub-sectors of the economy. The aerospace industry produces aircraft materials and parts for the public and private sectors. The five markets that the aerospace industry primarily serves are:

- Military aircraft
- Space planes
- Missiles
- General aviation
- Commercial aircraft are considered

First of all, it is crucial to be able to use the above two factors correctly. The ability to educate the new generation in accordance with the needs of the times, to establish fair rules in domestic and foreign economic activity, after the new industrial changes, will determine the results of getting on the path of "Rapid Development" or delaying it.

The biggest possibility in the current period is the lack of a perfect, final order of agreements and deals on how to use artificial intelligence among the leading countries.

That is, there are no legal obstacles for developing countries to join the process of using technologies of the fourth industrial revolution.

For comparison, we can observe that it was difficult to join this process when the norms of international law regarding the use of nuclear power were formed. Therefore, Uzbekistan should be able to make good use of internal and external enabling factors.

As a result of the scientific and technical revolution, the industrialized societies of the world are being transformed into a post-industrial society.

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